

Climate Change Rating of Countries 2024

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Abstract

This work applies a system of Climate Change Rating of countries (CCR). The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions over the last 30 years, and emissions change in the last 10 years.

The parameters are compared to conservatively determined world averages for every year.

The CCR for 2024 includes 214 countries, 99.9% of global CO₂ emissions and population, and 99.8% of global GDP.

The A-G labels for rating groups are according to the CCR limits. The best rating (A) is for the lowest CCR.

The average 2024 rating of Group A is 44 (46 in 2023) and of Group G 214 (212 in 2023). The CCR rating of Group A is 58% below the world average, and of Group G 112% above the world average.

The world average CCR value for 2024 is 101.68, equivalent to Group F.

In 2024 USA improved its CCR rating from 151.01 to 149.90. As the result it moved from Group G to Group F. This significantly decreased the CO₂ emissions of Group G from 62% of the global emissions to 49%.

The publication and linked website include the rating and details for each country. The CCR 2024 and details for each country are available online (free, no need to login) on site <https://nowagreen.ct.ws/ccr/2024/ccrcountry.php>.

Glossary

Σ GDP	cumulative GDP in last 30 years, ID
Ave	average
BL	baseline
cCO ₂	global cumulative CO ₂ emissions, CO ₂ emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO ₂
cCpGDP	country's cumulative CO ₂ emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period, tCO ₂ /ID
cCpGDPW	weight of parameter cCpGDP
CCR	Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work
cGDP	cumulative GDP in the last 30 years, ID
CGP	Conservative Global Parameter, decreasing only world parameter applied to the CCR
CO ₂	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂ , tCO ₂
CpC	country's CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
CpC10	country's change in CpC in last 10 years, %
CpC10W	weight of parameter CpC10
CpCW	weight of parameter CpC
CpGDP	country's CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /ID (ton CO ₂ per year, per (International Dollar 2017, per year))
CpGDP10	change in CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last 10 years, %
CpGDP10W	weight of parameter CpGDP10
CpGDPW	weight of parameter CpGDP
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant International Dollar 2017, ID/y
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline, °C

ID	constant International Dollar 2017
ktCO ₂ /y	kilo-ton CO ₂ = 1,000 metric tons of CO ₂ per year
MtCO ₂ /y	Mega-ton CO ₂ = 1,000,000 metric tons of CO ₂
OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [2] [3]
tcCO ₂	metric ton of cumulative CO ₂
tCO ₂	metric ton of CO ₂
tCO ₂ /y,cap	metric ton of CO ₂ per year, per capita
WB	World Bank
WCpC	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
WCpC10	CGP world change in CpC in last 10 years, %
WcCpGDP	CGP world cumulative CO ₂ emissions in last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period, tcCO ₂ /ID
WCpGDP	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /ID
WCpGDP10	CGP world change in CpGDP in last 10 years, %

Units

This work is in metric units.

The CO₂ emissions are in metric tons (tCO₂).

The GDP unit is constant International Dollar 2017 (ID).

Climate Change Rating of Countries

Nowagreen Climate Change Rating of Countries is described in the publication “*Climate Change Rating of Countries*” [1]. Publication [1] is related to the year 2020. The current publication is related to the Climate Change Rating of Countries in 2024.

Parameters Included in the Rating

Table 1 - Parameters included in the rating

Parameter	Country Symbol	World Symbol	Unit
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap
CO2 emissions per GDP	CpGDP	WCpGDP	tCO2/y,ID
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	cCpGDP	WcCpGDP	tcCO2/ID
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	WCpC10	%
Change in CpGDP in the last 10 years	CpGDP10	WCpGDP10	%

Weights of the CCR Parameters

Table 2 - CCR parameters weight

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Weight	Weight Symbol
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	25%	CpCW
CO2 emissions per GDP	CpGDP	25%	CpGDPW
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	cCpGDP	20%	cCpGDPW
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	15%	CpC10W
Change in CpGDP in the last 10 years	CpGDP10	15%	CpGDP10W
Σ	5	100%	

A higher value of the calculations' result means worse CCR (more CO2 emissions).

Sources of Data

The datasets are from the following sources:

- OWID [2] [3] CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included
- World Bank (WB) [4] GDP, PPP (constant 2021 international \$)

CO2 emissions are without international transport.

Table 3 - Dataset [2] [3] [4]

	CO2 emissions	GDP	Population
Source of data	OWID	World Bank/OWID/	OWID
Reference	[2]	[4] [3]	[3]
Countries	215	215	215
From year	1990	1990	1990
To year	2024	2024	2024
CO2 from fossil fuels	Yes		
CO2 from cement production	Yes		
CO2 from other sources	No		
Other GHG	No		
Land use change	No		
International transport	No		
Units	tCO2/y	Constant International \$ 2021	
Resolution	1 tCO2/y	1	1

Table 4 - Completeness of data

		Dataset	World	Dataset to World
countries		214	240	89.1667%
CO2 emissions	MtCO2/y	37,406	37,406	99.9999%
Population	Ex6	8,155	8,162	99.9156%
GDP	Ex9ID	148,581	149,003	99.7169%

Conversion of GDP Data

The GDP units in the WB publication [4] are “constant 2021 international \$”. However, the CCR for previous years is based on “2017 International \$”.

The WB [4] “2021 international \$” data were used to find the annual change in % in GDP for each country, assuming that the “2017 international \$” changes by the same percent.

World Data 2024

Table 5 - World data 2024

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2024
CO2 emissions in 2024		tCO2/y	37,406,135,000
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years		tcCO2	920,785,201,000
CO2 emissions 10 years ago		tCO2/y	34,345,785,000
Population			8,161,972,574
Population 10 years ago			7,339,013,632
GDP		ID/y	149,002,828,311,840
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years		cID	2,942,803,403,489,460
GDP 10 years ago		ID/y	104,018,222,159,394
CpC 10 years ago		tCO2/y,cap	4.6798912
CpGDP 10 years ago		tCO2/ID	0.000330190
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.5829773
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCpGDP	tCO2/ID	0.000251043
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WcCpGDP	tcCO2/ID	0.000312894
Last CpC to CpC 10 years ago	WCpC10	%	97.92914%
Last CpGDP to CpGDP 10 years ago	WCpGDP10	%	76.02988%

Table 6 - World data 2024 compared to 2023

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	2024	2023	Δ
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.58	4.57	+0.2%
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCpGDP	tCO2/ID	0.000251	0.000257	-2.2%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WcCpGDP	tcCO2/ID	0.000313	0.000318	-1.6%
Last CpC to CpC 10 years ago	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	97.93%	97.20%	+0.8%
Last CpGDP to CpGDP 10 years ago	CpGDP10	tCO2/ID	76.03%	80.80%	-5.9%

Conservative Global Parameters - CGP

The CCR world parameters change every year. The CCR world parameters change every year. There will be years when some world parameters increase, and some decrease. To ensure a conservative approach to the CCR, the “*Conservative Global Parameters*” (CGP) are applied each year, replacing the current year's actual world averages. If the world parameter value drops below the previous year's CGP value, the new CGP will change to the actual world parameter value.

If the world parameter value is above the last CGP, the current year's CGP will remain the same as the previous year's.

Table 7 - Conservative Global Parameters - CGP for 2024

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2024	CGP2023	CGP2024
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO ₂ /y,cap	4.58298	4.37774	4.37774
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCpGDP	tCO ₂ /y,ID	0.000251043	0.000256625	0.000251043
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WcCpGDP	tcCO ₂ /ID	0.000312894	0.000317908	0.000312894
Last CpC to CpC 10 years ago	CpC10	%	97.9291%	94.7267%	94.7267%
Last CpGDP to CpGDP 10 years ago	CpGDP10	%	76.0299%	79.8483%	76.0299%

Table 8 - CCR world parameters 2024

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2024	CGP2024	Value
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO ₂ /y,cap	4.58298	4.37774	104.69%
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCpGDP	tCO ₂ /y,ID	0.000251043	0.000251043	100.00%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WcCpGDP	tcCO ₂ /ID	0.000312894	0.000312894	100.00%
Last CpC to CpC 10 years ago	CpC10	%	97.9291%	94.7267%	103.38%
Last CpGDP to CpGDP 10 years ago	CpGDP10	%	76.0299%	76.0299%	100.00%

Table 9 - CCR Index for the World in 2024

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Weight	Index
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	104.69%	25%	26.17%
CO2 emissions per GDP	CpGDP	100.00%	25%	25.00%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	cCpGDP	100.00%	20%	20.00%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	103.38%	15%	15.51%
Change in CpGDP in the last 10 years	CpGDP10	100.00%	15%	15.00%
Σ			100%	101.68%

The CCR Index for the world in the year 2024 is 101.68 (101.69 in 2023).

Example of Denmark

Table 10 - Input parameters for CCR for Denmark

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Denmark	CGP2024	to CGP2024
CO2 emissions in 2024	CO2	tCO2/y	28,369,100		
Population			5,977,417		
GDP	GDP	ID/y	354,970,357,688		
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years	cCO2	tcCO2	1,398,695,600		
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years	cGDP	ID	8,673,697,805,488		
CpC 10 years ago		tCO2/y,cap	6.6502		
CpGDP 10 years ago		tCO2/y,ID	0.0001312		
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.7460	4.3777	108.41%
CO2 emissions per GDP	CpGDP	tCO2/y,ID	0.00007992	0.00025104	31.84%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	cCpGDP	tcCO2/ID	0.00016126	0.00031289	51.54%
Last CpC to CpC 10 years ago	CpC10	%	71.37%	94.73%	75.34%
Last CpGDP to CpGDP 10 years ago	CpGDP10	%	60.91%	76.03%	80.11%

Table 11 - CCR Index for Denmark in 2024

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Weight	Index
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	108.41%	25%	27.10%
CO2 emissions per GDP	CpGPT	31.84%	25%	7.96%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	cCpGPT	51.54%	20%	10.31%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	75.34%	15%	11.30%
Change in CpGDP in the last 10 years	CpGPT10	80.11%	15%	12.02%
Σ			100%	69%

The CCR Index for Denmark in the year 2024 is 69 (68 in 2023) (much better than the world average).

CCR details for each country are available on the website [6].

Table 12 - Denmark's CCR country page [6]

Nowagreen Climate Change Rating of Countries - CCR 2024	
country: Denmark (DNK) 2024	
country	Denmark
country code	DNK
CCR year	2024
CO2 emissions per capita (CpC), tCO2/y.cap	4.75
CpC to World	108%
CpC weight	27%
CO2 emissions per GDP (Cp\$), tCO2/\$GDP	8.0E-5
Cp\$ to World	32%
Cp\$ weight	11%
cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP (CCp\$\$), tCO2/\$GDP	0.000161
CCp\$\$ to World	52%
CCp\$\$ weight	10%
change in CO2 emissions per capita in the last 10 years (CpC10), tCO2/y.cap	71%
CpC10 to World	75%
CpC10 weight	11%
change in CO2 emissions per GDP in the last 10 years (Cp\$10), tCO2/\$GDP	62%
Cp\$10 to World	75%
Cp\$10 weight	12%
CCR Rating a lower number means less CO2 and a better rating	69
country position on the CCR list of a total 214	55
A-G CCR label	C

Rating A-G

Rating A-G includes 7 groups.

Table 13 - A-G groups

Rating	min CCR	max CCR	Color
A		50	Light Green
B	51	60	Dark Green
C	61	70	Light Blue
D	71	85	Dark Blue
E	86	100	Violet
F	101	150	Red
G	151		Black

Table 14 - Group A

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
A	12	44	List #	96,864,611
AGO	Angola	49	10	22,333,560
ETH	Ethiopia	42	5	17,837,310
CIV	Cote d'Ivoire	50	12	14,828,570
YEM	Yemen	39	2	10,123,040
CMR	Cameroon	45	6	9,631,580
UGA	Uganda	46	8	6,333,816
COD	Democratic Republic of Congo	36	1	5,904,450
ALB	Albania	50	11	4,444,440
NER	Niger	46	7	3,169,960
MAC	Macao	39	3	1,056,326
LBR	Liberia	41	4	859,370
GNB	Guinea-Bissau	48	9	342,189

Table 15 - Group B

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
B	21	56	List #	476,539,432
LIE	Liechtenstein	51	13	131624
MLT	Malta	52	14	1728770
BEN	Benin	53	15	6066336
NGA	Nigeria	55	20	135,824,600
BGD	Bangladesh	60	32	108,317,800
COL	Colombia	58	28	92,659,500
CHE	Switzerland	56	24	32,071,600
KEN	Kenya	53	16	21,225,400
GHA	Ghana	57	27	21,021,880
LKA	Sri Lanka	55	21	20,825,550
CRI	Costa Rica	55	23	8,760,460
MOZ	Mozambique	60	31	8,612,630
MDG	Madagascar	54	17	4,528,380
NAM	Namibia	57	26	3,469,116
HTI	Haiti	55	19	2,970,700
TCD	Chad	60	30	2,831,400
MWI	Malawi	60	33	1,881,480
SLE	Sierra Leone	54	18	1,434,284
SOM	Somalia	57	25	1,319,190
DJI	Djibouti	55	22	564,084
SLB	Solomon Islands	58	29	294,648

Table 16 - Group C

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
C	25	65	List #	1,479,040,277
BRA	Brazil	66	50	483,010,000
GBR	United Kingdom	70	58	312,906,000
FRA	France	66	51	264,157,000
PAK	Pakistan	61	34	179,800,600
SWE	Sweden	61	36	38,096,600
PRT	Portugal	63	41	35,539,000
HKG	Hong Kong	65	45	33,323,900
DNK	Denmark	69	55	28,369,100
TZA	Tanzania	66	49	20,018,370
GTM	Guatemala	65	46	19,880,410
PAN	Panama	62	38	12,664,410
AFG	Afghanistan	70	57	10,826,000
URY	Uruguay	69	56	7,973,270
PRY	Paraguay	62	39	7,936,720
NIC	Nicaragua	62	40	5,630,350
GAB	Gabon	64	44	5,398,820
GIN	Guinea	62	37	4,026,184
TGO	Togo	67	54	2,753,580
RWA	Rwanda	65	48	2,033,546
FJI	Fiji	66	53	1,445,320
SWZ	Eswatini	63	42	1,044,644
GMB	Gambia	61	35	802,776
TLS	East Timor	66	52	668,112
CPV	Cape Verde	65	47	593,786
STP	Sao Tome and Principe	64	43	141,779

Table 17 - Group D

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
D	50	79	List #	2,538,357,739
MEX	Mexico	81	91	460,989,000
ITA	Italy	81	87	301,930,000
EGY	Egypt	73	66	258,368,000
ESP	Spain	75	71	220,341,000
PHL	Philippines	80	86	174,878,300
ARG	Argentina	82	95	171,059,000
NLD	Netherlands	82	96	114,786,000
CHL	Chile	81	90	78,725,700
PER	Peru	79	84	70,246,700
MAR	Morocco	82	92	69,062,300
ROU	Romania	72	63	68,552,000
AUT	Austria	85	106	56,367,700
ISR	Israel	82	98	52,637,200
ECU	Ecuador	85	108	45,979,500
HUN	Hungary	77	80	40,016,900
NOR	Norway	83	100	37,182,900
IRL	Ireland	72	65	33,310,600
DOM	Dominican Republic	82	97	33,130,820
FIN	Finland	77	76	29,775,100
CUB	Cuba	84	104	24,440,200
JOR	Jordan	75	68	23,219,200
HRV	Croatia	85	107	18,464,900
SDN	Sudan	71	61	17,794,770
LBN	Lebanon	84	103	15,649,920
SEN	Senegal	76	73	14,091,840
HND	Honduras	77	78	12,854,850
LTU	Lithuania	77	79	12,541,600
GEO	Georgia	82	93	11,784,300
SLV	El Salvador	76	75	8,972,290
PNG	Papua New Guinea	72	64	8,345,460
BWA	Botswana	79	85	7,461,600
ARM	Armenia	77	77	7,430,720
MLI	Mali	75	69	6,978,840
BFA	Burkina Faso	75	70	6,507,660
LVA	Latvia	71	60	6,461,900
MDA	Moldova	78	81	5,326,900
MUS	Mauritius	82	94	4,673,616
MNE	Montenegro	83	102	2,376,260
SSD	South Sudan	76	72	1,695,552
PYF	French Polynesia	81	88	922,870
BDI	Burundi	85	105	916,664
LCA	Saint Lucia	82	99	536,909
AND	Andorra	81	89	424,663
VCT	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	74	67	255,657
WSM	Samoa	71	59	245,587
VUT	Vanuatu	71	62	197,079
VGB	British Virgin Islands	76	74	192,507
DMA	Dominica	79	83	170,858
KIR	Kiribati	79	82	72,456
SHN	Saint Helena	83	101	11,391

Table 18 - Group E

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
E	37	93	List #	5,861,923,319
IND	India	96	133	3,193,480,000
IDN	Indonesia	97	135	812,220,000
DEU	Germany	89	116	572,330,000
TUR	Turkey	100	144	513,035,000
THA	Thailand	88	113	267,760,700
BEL	Belgium	97	134	85,456,000
SGP	Singapore	99	143	53,919,400
GRC	Greece	86	110	53,360,400
TUN	Tunisia	93	128	32,663,660
NZL	New Zealand	88	115	32,479,400
BGR	Bulgaria	90	118	31,621,700
MMR	Myanmar	88	112	31,603,440
SVK	Slovakia	92	127	29,091,000
BOL	Bolivia	98	136	28,708,660
NPL	Nepal	93	130	18,776,080
ZWE	Zimbabwe	99	142	13,701,160
SVN	Slovenia	92	126	12,751,240
ZMB	Zambia	91	123	12,043,290
KGZ	Kyrgyzstan	87	111	11,770,100
TJK	Tajikistan	94	132	10,739,780
EST	Estonia	93	131	8,306,800
CYP	Cyprus	91	121	7,299,320
MKD	North Macedonia	91	120	6,619,670
MRT	Mauritania	86	109	5,238,680
PSE	Palestine Authority	98	137	4,780,050
GUY	Guyana	92	125	4,510,330
MDV	Maldives	98	138	2,306,210
BTN	Bhutan	88	114	1,657,416
BLZ	Belize	93	129	796,026
ERI	Eritrea	99	141	742,646
SYC	Seychelles	99	139	652,571
BMU	Bermuda	91	122	550,000
GRD	Grenada	99	140	376,971
KNA	Saint Kitts and Nevis	100	145	259,757
TON	Tonga	90	117	152,540
BES	Bonaire Sint Eustatius and Saba	90	119	151,882
TUV	Tuvalu	91	124	11,440

Table 19 - Group F

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
F	41	120	List #	8,586,099,974
USA	United States	150	186	4,904,090,000
JPN	Japan	105	152	961,870,000
KOR	South Korea	138	182	583,679,000
VNM	Vietnam	118	165	370,931,700
MYS	Malaysia	127	176	290,223,500
POL	Poland	108	155	272,861,000
TWN	Taiwan	133	181	262,345,000
DZA	Algeria	120	167	198,203,300
UKR	Ukraine	116	162	142,497,000
UZB	Uzbekistan	144	184	139,234,300
VEN	Venezuela	101	146	116,042,200
CZE	Czechia	101	148	75,623,000
BLR	Belarus	123	168	55,818,300
SRB	Serbia	129	178	42,019,300
AZE	Azerbaijan	106	153	39,830,200
SYR	Syria	114	159	31,778,600
KHM	Cambodia	127	175	21,882,690
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	130	179	19,425,900
COG	Congo	126	172	8,839,770
JAM	Jamaica	103	150	8,401,760
XKX	Kosovo	127	174	8,049,930
LUX	Luxembourg	102	149	7,039,700
GNQ	Equatorial Guinea	104	151	7,010,350
ISL	Iceland	116	161	3,803,030
BHS	Bahamas	118	163	3,069,680
SUR	Suriname	113	158	2,987,770
LSO	Lesotho	118	164	2,571,770
BRB	Barbados	110	156	1,365,174
ABW	Aruba	123	170	920,640
FRO	Faroe Islands	150	185	725,388
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	131	180	665,140
GRL	Greenland	142	183	618,964
COM	Comoros	126	173	551,650
CAF	Central African Republic	106	154	394,681
TCA	Turks and Caicos Islands	129	177	378,842
FSM	Micronesia (country)	112	157	150,626
COK	Cook Islands	124	171	80,083
SPM	Saint Pierre and Miquelon	119	166	55,322
WLF	Wallis and Futuna	123	169	30,508
MSR	Montserrat	116	160	26,579
NIU	Niue	101	147	7,627

Table 20 - Group G

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
G	28	214	List #	18,367,274,768
CHN	China	163	191	12,289,040,000
RUS	Russia	179	197	1,780,520,000
IRN	Iran	172	195	792,631,000
SAU	Saudi Arabia	211	202	692,135,000
CAN	Canada	156	188	533,340,000
ZAF	South Africa	164	193	439,830,000
AUS	Australia	164	192	386,732,000
KAZ	Kazakhstan	202	201	287,005,000
IRQ	Iraq	157	190	233,635,300
ARE	United Arab Emirates	195	198	221,987,600
KWT	Kuwait	302	212	129,518,600
QAT	Qatar	351	214	125,812,200
OMN	Oman	198	200	82,662,000
TKM	Turkmenistan	229	205	81,005,600
LBY	Libya	152	187	65,260,100
PRK	North Korea	297	211	62,550,300
MNG	Mongolia	270	210	44,693,890
BHR	Bahrain	253	208	39,003,500
TTO	Trinidad and Tobago	323	213	34,576,300
LAO	Laos	214	203	24,399,930
BRN	Brunei	256	209	12,052,480
NCL	New Caledonia	231	206	5,286,640
CUW	Curacao	217	204	2,289,630
SXM	Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	198	199	717,644
PLW	Palau	247	207	226,099
MHL	Marshall Islands	167	194	154,480
AIA	Anguilla	173	196	148,085
NRU	Nauru	157	189	61,390

Table 21 - A-G CCR groups in 2024

Rating	countries	%	Ave CCR	tCO2/y	%
A	12	6%	44	96,864,611	0%
B	21	10%	56	476,539,432	1%
C	25	12%	65	1,479,040,277	4%
D	50	23%	79	2,538,357,739	7%
E	37	17%	93	5,861,923,319	16%
F	41	19%	120	8,586,099,974	23%
G	28	13%	214	18,367,274,768	49%
Σ	214	100%		37,406,100,120	100%

Countries with CCR Below and Above the World Average

The world CCR in 2024 is 101.68 (101.69 in 2023).

Table 22 - Countries with CCR below and above the world average in 2024

	Countries	%	tCO ₂ /y	%
CCR<101.68	149	70%	10,651,437,905	28%
CCR>101.68	65	30%	26,754,662,215	72%
Σ	214		37,406,100,120	

70% of countries have a CCR rating better than the world average in 2024. However, a 30% minority of countries with a CCR worse than the world average is responsible for 72% of global CO₂ emissions.

Table 23 - A-D and E-G CCR groups in 2024

Rating	countries	%	Ave CCR	tCO ₂ /y	%
A-D	110	51%	61	4,572,952,099	12%
E-G	104	49%	141	32,438,337,931	88%

Table 24 - Group G (the worst group) and all others in 2024

Rating	countries	%	Ave CCR	tCO ₂ /y	%
G	28	13%	214	18,367,274,768	49%
other	186	87%	83	19,038,825,352	51%

Group G, with its 28 countries, is responsible for 49% of global CO₂ emissions in 2024. Its average CCR rating is 214 (more than twice the CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP of the global average), compared to an average of 83 (less than the global average) for all other groups of 186 countries.

In 2024 USA improved its CCR rating from 151.01 to 149.90. As the result it moved from Group G to Group F. This significantly decreased the CO₂ emissions of Group G from 62% of the global emissions to 49%.

Table 25 - Trends of Group G (the worst group)

	countries	CCR	tCO ₂ /y	to World
2020	28	210	16,440,549,561	47.91%
2021	29	212	22,179,477,991	61.45%
2022	28	206	21,938,824,834	60.77%
2023	29	212	23,089,464,989	62.38%
2024	28	214	18,367,274,768	49.10%

Table 26 - Three countries of Group G with the highest emissions in 2024

	China	Russia	Iran	World
CO ₂ emissions, tCO ₂ /y	12,289,040,000	1,780,520,000	792,631,000	
change/y	+1.0%	+2.7%	+0.4%	+1.1%
CCR	163	179	172	102
to World	161%	176%	169%	
change/y	+0.4%	+2.0%	-0.5%	
#/214 countries	191	197	195	
change/y	-2	0	0	

Climate Change Rating of Countries on the Website

The Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work for the years 2020-2024 is available on the website [5].

Details of a specific country can be retrieved on site [6].

Table 27 - Climate Change Rating of Countries 2024 on the Website [6]

Nowgreen Climate Change Rating of Countries - CCR 2024 sorted by country code				
for more details click on country code				
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
ABW	Aruba	123	170	F
AFG	Afghanistan	70	57	C
AGO	Angola	49	10	A
AIA	Anguilla	173	196	G
ALB	Albania	50	11	A
AND	Andorra	81	89	D
ARE	United Arab Emirates	195	198	G
ARG	Argentina	82	95	D
ARM	Armenia	77	77	D
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	131	180	F
AUS	Australia	164	192	G
AUT	Austria	85	106	D
AZE	Azerbaijan	106	153	F
BDI	Burundi	85	105	D
BEL	Belgium	97	134	E
BEN	Benin	53	15	B
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
BES	Bonaire Sint Eustatius and Saba	90	119	E
BFA	Burkina Faso	75	70	D
BGD	Bangladesh	60	32	B
BGR	Bulgaria	90	118	E
BHR	Bahrain	253	208	G
BHS	Bahamas	118	163	F
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	130	179	F
BLR	Belarus	123	168	F
BLZ	Belize	93	129	E
BMU	Bermuda	91	122	E
BOL	Bolivia	98	136	E
BRA	Brazil	66	50	C
BRB	Barbados	110	156	F
BRN	Brunei	256	209	G
BTN	Bhutan	88	114	E
BWA	Botswana	79	85	D

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